

KEY ISSUES WITH RESIDUAL FATIGUE LIFE ESTIMATION IN STEELS, HIGHLY SCATTERED AND NON-CONSERVATIVE THRESHOLDS, CRACK CLOSURE MECHANISMS, INFLUENCING FACTORS, RELEVANT MATERIAL PROPERTIES

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Fatigue crack growth rates for three different steels at room temperature were measured at high and low load ratios. The loading components and mechanisms in terms of effective ΔK , plasticity-, roughness- and oxide-induced crack closure were separated, including the threshold. The plasticity-induced crack closure values were modified according to the material cyclic plastic behaviour. The influencing factors on oxide debris growth such as loading history and air humidity are discussed. A model for simulation of oxide debris growth is introduced. The approach to fatigue crack growth modelling considering all these effects is presented, which contributes to a clarification of the influencing factors and to reaching the aim of transferability of the fatigue crack growth data into applications. It is pointed out that the lack of consideration of oxide-induced crack closure can lead to several non-conservative or misleading scenarios.

Keywords: Crack closure, Threshold, Life prediction, Steel

INTRODUCTION

Prediction of residual fatigue life (RFL) is one of the important tasks of materials scientists and engineers. The damage tolerance approach is applied in sectors where safety is the most critical factor, such as transportation or power industry.

When the commonly known concepts for prediction of fatigue crack propagation rate are employed, it is sometimes found that they do not work correctly due to many unresolved issues. The aim of the present work is to identify the key issues and to suggest how they can be solved. An improvement of the RFL estimations that is needed is closely related to the effects of loading history and load ratio. Plasticity-induced crack closure (PICC) can be used for simulation of both of these effects and it is one of the main focuses of the presented analysis.

The second main mechanism in focus is the oxide-induced crack closure (OICC), which is active in the near-threshold regime and which diminishes the crack driving force by the wedging effect of accumulation of oxide debris between the fracture surfaces in corroding steels. Variation of the fatigue crack growth threshold due to OICC has significant consequences for RFLs. It may seem that if the OICC effect is just omitted, the analyses will be conservative because the effect strengthens the material. However, the problem lies in the standard threshold measurement

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techniques which are usually affected by oxide debris production, thus providing non-conservative values. Moreover, the OICC effect depends on many factors and is responsible for the typical scatter and confusion related to the thresholds.

Although the crack closure phenomena have been studied already for decades, there are still particular problems and unanswered questions. Many lack suggestions on how to implement the results into the whole methodology of RFL computation. The present work focuses on providing such suggestions.

PLASTICITY-INDUCED CRACK CLOSURE

In order to study the individual crack closure mechanisms and to separate their influences, it is necessary to clarify PICC first, since this is the dominant mechanism determining the most significant effects such as the effects of load ratio and variable amplitude. The works by Newman et al. [1,2] resulted in a wide use of the strip-yield model (SYM) for prediction of PICC under variable-amplitude loading and also in the use of the equations for PICC implemented in the NASGRO code [3].

Improvement of the dependence of PICC on material

It was revealed by Kubíček et al. [4] that the variation of the load ratio effect in different steels was much larger than what the PICC models were able to predict or explain. It is a general problem of the PICC models based on continuum mechanics that they cannot grasp sufficiently the specifics of the material cyclic behaviour. The present approach emphasises that the description of material behaviour by means of monotonic stress-strain data is not sufficient for such complex phenomena as PICC under cyclic loading. The lack of consideration of cyclic softening/hardening or deformation irreversibility results in the modelled PICC values being practically constant for all materials, which is neither probable, nor observed.

This is why the presented approach suggests determining the PICC values experimentally but not in the way of crack closure measurements by means of the stiffness changes. There is a lot of debate, e.g. by González et al. [5] about the reliability of these techniques. Although particular laboratories are likely to develop their own reliable methodologies, it is questionable whether crack closure measurement can be considered reliable in a standardised and general sense. It is suggested that the amount of crack closure in a given material should not be measured but extracted from the observed load ratio effect by means of measurement of the corresponding crack growth rates. This, however, does not mean that the crack closure models are excluded from the analysis. On the contrary, the models calibrated by the observed material behaviour should be able to predict more accurately the crack growth rates under arbitrary load ratio and variable amplitude. The suggested methodology is not more demanding experimentally than the methodology of NASGRO, as demonstrated in the following paragraphs.

The crack growth rates for three different steels were experimentally obtained using the compact tension specimens of the thickness of 5 mm at room temperature.

'Material_1' is the 44MnSiV4 ferritic-pearlitic steel, which has the dominant portion of pearlite (70%) in the microstructure and it is used for fabrication of components in automotive. It has the yield stress of 660 MPa, the ultimate tensile strength of 960 MPa and the cyclic yield stress of 685 MPa.

'Material_2' is the low carbon steel alloyed by Cr and Mn quenched to bainite (25CrMo4) used in manufacturing of axles of railway vehicles. The yield stress is 581 MPa, the ultimate tensile strength is 727 MPa and the cyclic yield stress is 470 MPa.

'Material_3' is the austenitic stainless steel 304L (X2CrNi18-9) produced by laser powder-bed fusion annealed below the recrystallisation temperature to reduce the residual stress but to keep the microstructure originated during the additive manufacturing, which has a very fine (sub-micron) cellular structure in the grains responsible for a relatively large yield stress of 592 MPa and ultimate tensile strength of 780 MPa. The cyclic yield stress (obtained from the cyclic stress strain curve points for the half-life to failure) is 442 MPa. See [4] for details about the microstructure and chemical composition of all three materials.

The obtained crack growth rates are presented in Fig. 1 for the load ratio $R = 0.1$ (crosses) and for the high load ratio (solid line), which was $R = 0.8$ in Material_1 and Material_2, and $R = 0.7$ in Material_3. The results obtained at both of these high load ratios can be considered as the effective crack growth rate data ($\Delta K = \Delta K_{eff}$). The dashed line represents the theoretical values for $R = 0.1$ that would be obtained by addition of the PICC effect to the effective crack growth rate data. The selected crack closure function value $f = K_{cl}/K_{max} = 0.3$ was chosen as the typical value predicted by PICC models for the constraint factor $\alpha = 2.5$ which is close to the plane strain state relevant for fatigue testing specimens under small-scale yielding. It can clearly be seen that the experimental data for $R = 0.1$ for the investigated materials are not in agreement with the prediction using this f value.

In the presented approach, the f values were found empirically by moving of the theoretical dashed line to the experimental data in the Paris regime. In the near-threshold regime, additional closure components are present so the fits could not match the experimental data there. The empirical values of f were 0.5, 0.2 and 0.1 for Material_1, Material_2 and Material_3, respectively.

FIGURE 1 Experimental crack growth rates for Material_1 (blue), Material_2 (red) and Material_3 (green) obtained at a high load ratio (solid line) and at a low load ratio (isolated crosses). The dashed line represents the theoretical growth rates for $R = 0.1$ that would be obtained by addition of the PICC effect to the effective crack growth rate data using the crack closure value $f = 0.3$.

It was suggested in [4] that the ratio of sizes of the monotonic and the cyclic plastic zones is the quantity determining the amount of the PICC effect rather than just monotonic plasticity. In relation to this, the irreversibility of plastic deformation given by the material microstructure is an important feature to be studied to explain the observed PICC values. In the predominantly pearlitic steel (Material_1), the free dislocation path between the cementite lamellae is very short, resulting in limited dislocation structure development and the related almost stable cyclic behaviour. In addition, the plastic deformation of pearlite involves brittle fracture of the cementite lamellae, which adds much more to the overall irreversibility of plastic deformation. This is how the high

closure value $f = 0.5$ is explained in this material. The bainitic structure of Material_2 has a fine microstructure (characteristic distance between the barriers of $\approx 5 \mu\text{m}$) but the dislocation free path is larger than in Material_1. The relatively high yield stress is associated with the high dislocation density in the deformed grains of bainite. Under cyclic loading, new dislocation structure is formed in the slip bands, causing cyclic softening. This is why the material has a somewhat smaller closure value $f = 0.2$ than expected from the classical models. The submicron cellular structure of Material_3 is disrupted during cyclic loading, leading to an unusually high effect of cyclic softening, where the dislocation paths in the slip bands are much larger than in the original structure associated with the relatively high monotonic yield stress. This explains how the PICC effect could completely vanish in this material ($f = R$). Interestingly, the crack closure vanished also in the near-threshold regime, which can be explained by the lack of contact between fracture surfaces that is necessary for the development of roughness-induced crack closure (RICC) and OICC.

In order to take the described material differences into account, a so far unused parameter of the strip-yield model was suggested to be a variable, reflecting the irreversibility of plastic deformation. The constraint factors are the only variables affecting the PICC values significantly in this model. The constraint factor in tension α already has its physical meaning of the out-of-plane constraint. The constraint factor in compression β was chosen to manipulate the ratio between material stretching in tension and squeezing in compression, causing the desired variation of the cyclic plastic zone size with respect to the monotonic plastic zone size.

In general, the presence of brittle phases and cyclic hardening leads to a large irreversibility, large β values, and, consequently, large PICC values. Cyclic softening and the mechanism of fatigue crack propagation purely by means of blunting and re-sharpening of the crack tip lead to a good reversibility, small β values and small PICC values. Considering the f values fitted to the experiments, the corresponding β values were found by means of the curve in Fig. 2 (left) obtained by simulations of crack growth under constant amplitude loading with different β values in the FASTRAN software [6]. The obtained β values for the three investigated materials were taken as their characteristic parameters and were then used to build the diagram in Fig. 2 (right) showing the general dependence of the crack closure f on the load ratio R for $\alpha = 2.5$. The β values can be used universally as material parameters in any simulations including crack propagation under variable-amplitude loading, reaching the desired ability of the model to be dependent on material.

FIGURE 2 Constraint factors in compression β determined for the empirically obtained f values (left) and the corresponding collection of the computed f dependences on the load ratio R (right) for the three investigated materials (blue, red and green colour) and for the classical value of $\beta = 1$ (black colour).

Adopting the results of retardation and acceleration effects for analytical expression

The RFL computation procedure needs to consider other effects than PICC, such as oxide-induced crack closure, residual stress profile or crack shape evolution in various components, which has been challenging to implement into the strip-yield model. Therefore, a more general code for fatigue crack propagation simulation has been developed with the necessity of input of the variable-amplitude loading effects. The equations based on the model by Willenborg et al. [7,8] are sometimes used. However, such kind of models predict an immediate crack retardation after the overload, which does not happen in real cracks and, consequently, the use of these simulations can lead to non-conservative predictions. It is intended to replace these models by a PICC model in order to correctly describe the delayed retardation effects.

In the present work, the results of crack retardation and acceleration effects during transitions between different loading amplitudes due to PICC were extracted from FASTRAN to form a set of analytical equations describing the evolution of the corrected crack closure function f over the crack extension after the overload/underload. Promising results were obtained for a constant R ratio. The process of completion of the equations for more general cases is currently running.

Overload effect on thresholds obtained by load shedding

The fatigue crack growth threshold values obtained by the standard load shedding technique are affected by PICC overload effects. The significance of this effect was studied by means of simulations run in FASTRAN. The results showed that if the load decreasing was continuous with the rate corresponding to a decrease of 5% and 15% of the load after each crack extension of 0.1 mm, the variation of the obtained thresholds was only 6%. On the other hand, when the load was decreased stepwise after each crack extension of 0.1 mm, the thresholds were different by 14%, which is already a notable influence of the overloads, especially considering the possibility of a crack arrest in real cracks by the development of oxide debris at fracture surfaces during the retarded crack growth.

OXIDE-INDUCED CRACK CLOSURE

The analysis of PICC, on which the previous chapter was focused, provided the basis for studying of the additional closure mechanisms, from which the oxide-induced crack closure is the most significant one in corroding steels.

Mechanism and influencing factors

The presence of PICC or RICC is required for the fracture surfaces to get into contact. The contact promotes friction and high compressive stress between the fracture surfaces in the vicinity of the crack tip. This leads to a disruption of the passivation oxide layer and an exposure of the new metallic surface available for oxidation in each cycle. After many repetitions, typically several millions of cycles in the near-threshold regime, the oxide debris accumulates to form the so-called enhanced oxide layer with the thicknesses of about hundreds of nanometres. It is a mechanism similar to fretting. It was verified by Pokorný et al. [9] that leaving the crack open for a long time without cyclic loading does not lead to oxide debris formation. Therefore, both conditions have to be fulfilled in order to produce the OICC effect: large compressive stress and many repetitions of

the contact and the same place. This is not fulfilled at fracture surfaces far behind the crack tip or during crack propagation at higher rates than approx. 10^{-6} mm/cycle.

The oxidic layers and their thickness were observed in [9] and by Vojtek et al. [10] by means of special cuts produced by focused ion beam milling in a scanning electron microscope. At a macroscopic view, the enhanced oxide debris deposit is visible on the fracture surfaces as dark brown or black spots with the highest intensity just behind the crack tip position corresponding to the crack arrest. Fig. 3 presents fracture surfaces with the oxide debris accumulation visible after $3 \cdot 10^5$ cycles and $3 \cdot 10^6$ cycles in normal humid air and after $3 \cdot 10^6$ cycles in dry air, where no enhanced oxide debris was observed.

FIGURE 3 Fracture surfaces showing different amounts of oxide debris accumulation in the vicinity of the line of crack arrest after application of the shown number of cycles in humid and dry air.

Air humidity is one of the most influencing factors of oxide debris growth and it should be controlled in laboratories in order to assess the relevancy of the results. Variation of the threshold $K_{\max,th}$ from approx. 4 to 7 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ due to air humidity was reported in [10] for a railway axle steel. The highest value from this range is usually the one measured in most laboratories in normal air humidity. This means that in operation at winter temperatures, where the lowest humidity from the measured interval commonly occurs, the actual threshold can reach only 60% of the value determined in summer in a laboratory. The tests in dry air were performed using a special sealed chamber containing silica gel balls attached to the specimen, sealed but mechanically isolated not to influence the inertia mass, see Pokorný et al. [11] for details.

A very similar effect on the oxide debris formation was observed by Tazoe et al. [12] at different loading frequencies, in particular, the thresholds were as low as in the dry air at frequencies below approx. 5 to 20 Hz. The laboratory testing machines usually operate at about 50 – 100 Hz, resulting in the same dangerous non-conservativeness as in the previous case, any time of the year.

Yet another effect causing a similar range of variation of threshold is the specimen thickness, which was reported by Maierhofer et al. [13]. It was observed that the oxide debris was produced more efficiently in the middle part of the specimens than close to the free surface. The edge effect created the dependence of threshold on thickness. It is hypothesised that this is related to the length

of the path available for air flow running from the outside of the specimen to the crack tip. Cyclic crack opening and closure results in dynamic air pressure changes inside the crack, which are larger for longer air flow paths. Both the effect of specimen thickness and the effect of loading frequency could be related to these pressure changes. In the experiments by [13], the air flow paths were closed by gluing a rubber tape over the crack growth area of the specimen side surface, causing the oxide debris to grow uniformly along the whole thickness. The dependence of threshold on specimen thickness vanished and the obtained thresholds were significantly larger. Assessment of this effect in real cracks in engineering components is challenging due to their different geometry, see also the comment about semi-elliptical cracks at the end of the article.

Strategy for crack closure component decomposition and crack growth simulation

Due to the significance of the OICC effect, it is suggested that one more crack growth rate curve should be measured in dry air at the same low load ratio as the one measured in normal (humid) air. Counting only one curve for a high load ratio, such a set of three curves allows performing of a complete crack closure analysis.

The difference between thresholds measured at humid and dry air reveals the material sensitivity to the OICC effect, describing the range of variation of OICC from zero to a typical value obtained under particular testing arrangement. The knowledge of this range is important for assessment of the possible variation of threshold in operation due to the above described effects on OICC, thus explaining the typical scatter of the values. The dry-air threshold can serve as a conservative value representing a 'true' threshold, which is characteristic for a material and independent of the external factors. Application of this approach has important consequences for the research of crack closure mechanisms, providing a step on the way to reach transferability of the laboratory data to real components or between specimens with various geometries.

The proposed methodology begins with the measurement of one da/dN vs. ΔK curve for a high load ratio (e.g. 0.8) and two curves at a low load ratio, e.g. (0.1 or -1), one in normal humid air and one in a dry-air chamber to obtain data not affected by OICC. Then, estimation of the crack closure function f from the difference between the crack growth rates in the Paris regime is done, as described in the previous chapter. To find the value of f , the relationship (1) is used:

$$\Delta K_{R=0.8} = \Delta K_{low R} \cdot U = \Delta K_{low R} \cdot \left(\frac{1-f}{1-R}\right) \quad (1)$$

The experimentally modified f value can be reached in the NASGRO procedure by manipulation of the constraint factor α or by finding the related constraint factor in compression β in FASTRAN. After that, an ordinary fitting procedure of the coefficients of the NASGRO equation (2) is done to make the equation complete (omitting the final fracture term for simplicity).

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \left[\Delta K \left(\frac{1-f}{1-R} \right) \right]^m \left(1 - \frac{\Delta K_{th}}{\Delta K} \right)^p \quad (2)$$

The threshold in terms of $K_{max,th}$ obtained in dry air is subtracted from that obtained in humid air to obtain the quantity K_{ox} , which is defined to express the effect of oxide debris on crack growth. At threshold, it has the value $K_{ox,th}$.

$$K_{ox,th} = K_{max,th, humid air} - K_{max,th, dry air} \quad (3)$$

For the decomposition of mechanisms, the relation $\Delta K_{eff} = K_{max} - K_{cl}$ is written with the individual closure components as follows:

$$\Delta K_{\text{eff}} = K_{\text{max}} - f \cdot K_{\text{max}} - K_{\text{RICC}} - K_{\text{PICC,VAL}} - K_{\text{ox}}, \quad (4)$$

where $K_{\text{PICC,VAL}}$ is the term considering the effects of plasticity-induced crack closure due to variable amplitude loading and K_{RICC} is the part remaining for the roughness-induced crack closure. The NASGRO equation (2) contains the threshold term, which does not allow a direct expression of the actual ΔK_{eff} . It can, however, be done by the following trick. First, for a given ΔK and R , the da/dN has to be computed and then, for the same da/dN , the corresponding ΔK at $R = 0.8$ is found, which is presumed to be effective and it is denoted as $\Delta K_{\text{eff,N}}$. Since the NASGRO equation coefficients were fitted to the data from dry air under constant-amplitude loading, the relationship between $\Delta K_{\text{eff,N}}$ and the decomposition in Eq. (4) is:

$$\Delta K_{\text{eff}} = \Delta K_{\text{eff,N}} - K_{\text{PICC,VAL}} - K_{\text{ox}}, \quad (5)$$

which means that

$$\Delta K_{\text{eff,N}} = K_{\text{max}} - f \cdot K_{\text{max}} - K_{\text{RICC}}. \quad (6)$$

The K_{RICC} component appeared because of the threshold term in the NASGRO equation. Note that in order to find the f function in the Paris regime at the beginning of the procedure, the K_{RICC} component was assumed to be zero.

To obtain the resulting crack growth rate, the 'true' ΔK_{eff} taking all effects into account is put into the NASGRO equation for $R = 0.8$ and the final value of da/dN is computed. Interestingly, using such a decomposition of mechanisms, it is possible to evaluate RICC, which is very difficult, if possible, by any other way, both experimentally and theoretically. The decomposition is also interesting at threshold, where it can be written as:

$$K_{\text{max,th}} = \Delta K_{\text{eff,th}} + f \cdot K_{\text{max,th}} + K_{\text{RICC,th}} + K_{\text{PICC,VAL,th}} + K_{\text{ox,th}}. \quad (7)$$

The effective threshold is a remarkably predictable parameter. It can be estimated only by the basic crystal structure parameters, the Young modulus E and the magnitude of the Burgers vector b according to the relation $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}} \approx 3/4 \cdot E b^{1/2}$ for pure metals and $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}} \approx E b^{1/2}$ for alloys, see Pohluda et al. [14]. It does not depend on the microstructural state or the yield stress.

Plasticity-induced crack closure (under constant amplitude loading) at threshold is simply taken as the same value as that found in the Paris regime. Although this is a simplification and the plasticity at threshold is discretised at the atomic level, the results of discrete dislocation models by Riemelmoser et al. and Pohluda et al. [15,16] estimate the PICC values to be very close to the those obtained by continuum mechanics. Hence this simplification is acceptable.

The component of PICC under variable amplitude loading was discussed in terms of the overload effect during load shedding. If required, it can be taken into account in the decomposition. In the further text, it is neglected for simplicity.

The last component $K_{\text{ox,th}}$ is determined by Eq. (3) and it reveals information about the intensity of the OICC effect in the given material. The value also serves as a material fitting parameter in the quantitative cycle-by-cycle model of K_{ox} introduced further in this article.

Decomposition of the threshold values

The decomposition at threshold is expressed graphically in Fig. 4 for the three investigated materials for humid and dry air. In can be seen that the thresholds are as different as 9, 6, and

$3 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, which is caused purely by the crack closure phenomena, since $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$ was approx. $2.7 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ in all three steels. The $K_{\text{ox,th}}$ component represents a possible variation of the threshold due to the factors influencing oxide debris growth. It should be noted that, in fact, the component denoted as K_{ox} is a combination of OICC and an increase in PICC, since K_{max} is larger. These effects, however, are both present as a consequence of the occurrence of OICC. Thus, for modelling, the total change of closure because of OICC should be expressed in the sense of Fig. 4.

FIGURE 4 Decomposition of the threshold values $K_{\text{max,th}}$ into the closure components and $\Delta K_{\text{eff,th}}$ for the three investigated materials in humid air and in dry air.

From a certain point of view, the threshold without the loading history effects can be considered as a conservative value acting as a material characteristic. For this value, the related decomposition is obtained by omission of the last two components in Eq. (7):

$$K_{\text{max,th, material}} = \Delta K_{\text{eff,th}} + f \cdot K_{\text{max,th}} + K_{\text{RICC,th}}, \quad (8)$$

suggesting the relationship (9).

$$K_{\text{max,th, affected}} = K_{\text{max,th, material}} + K_{\text{PICC,VAL,th}} + K_{\text{ox,th}} \quad (9)$$

The next section is focused on the proposal of a methodology to determine the dependence of K_{ox} on the loading history.

Model of evolution of OICC under cyclic loading

Preliminary results of the model under development are presented for Material_2. The dynamics of oxide debris growth was defined by two equations, Eq. (10) related to the growth of the oxide debris layer at each cycle, and Eq. (11) related to the decrease of K_{ox} due to travelling of the new crack tip away by the distance da corresponding to the crack extension in the current cycle. The parameter N_{fict} is taken from the previous cycle according to Eq. (12), which ensures the continuity of growth of K_{ox} from its current value.

$$K_{\text{ox},i} = K_{\text{lim}} \left(1 - e^{-v_{\text{ox}} \sqrt{N_{\text{fict},i+1}}} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$K_{\text{ox},i+1} = K_{\text{ox},i} - da \frac{K_{\text{lim}}}{z_{\text{max}}} \quad (11)$$

$$N_{\text{fict},i+1} = \left[\frac{1}{v_{\text{ox}}} \ln \left(1 - \frac{K_{\text{ox},i+1}}{K_{\text{lim}}} \right) \right]^2 \quad (12)$$

The parameter K_{lim} expresses the maximum value, to which K_{ox} can grow, which depends on material, environment, specimen thickness etc. For the presented results this value was $3 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$. The parameter z_{max} expresses crack extension, after which the zone of the influence of K_{ox} decays. The parameter v_{ox} expresses how quickly K_{ox} grows. The values of z_{max} and v_{ox} were estimated based on the data published in [9] for a cyclically loaded stationary crack. Typically, the enhanced oxide layer after several millions of cycles has the thickness of 200 to 400 nanometres.

After computation of K_{ox} , the value was inserted into the crack propagation strategy described above in order to grow the crack. The results are presented in Fig. 5. The external loading corresponded to a stepwise load-shedding test at $R = 0.1$, from which the experimental data are shown by blue symbols. The crack stopped at the apparent threshold of approx. $6.5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$. The threshold from dry air was considered in the simulation, which was $K_{max,th} = 4 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$. Fig. 5(a) shows the results of the simulation with the oxide debris model turned off ($K_{ox} = 0$) for comparison. Fig. 5(b) presents the results with the evolution of K_{ox} simulated, where the crack arrest appeared at approx. $6.2 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$. The number of loading cycles corresponding to the crack arrest was approx. $1.8 \cdot 10^6$, after which the value of K_{ox} was further growing, see Fig. 5(c). The simulation was able to predict a larger increase of threshold due to K_{ox} than the increase caused by the PICC overload effects. Thus, using this model, the apparent thresholds can be estimated and in the case of no dry air experimental setup available, the decomposition of threshold into the closure components can be helped by a simulation of oxide debris growth during the particular loading history and the measurement method. Considering the well predictability of $\Delta K_{eff,th}$, this is a step to reach a reasonable predictability also for thresholds under low load ratios.

Note that the evolution of the simulated crack growth rates at the two lowest load levels resembles behaviour of short cracks, which is a consequence of the oxide debris growth during very small crack growth rates.

FIGURE 5 The results of the crack propagation simulation during a load shedding test in terms of the growth rates vs. the applied load K_{max} for (a) no oxide debris influence and for (b) dynamic evolution of K_{ox} (oxide-induced crack closure) during the test. (c) shows the dependence of K_{ox} on the number of applied cycles.

REMARKS TO OTHER ISSUES

Dependence of threshold on crack length (cyclic R-curve)

The dependence of threshold on crack length is the cyclic R-curve, which was measured, e.g. by Pourheidar et al. and Maierhofer et al. [17,18]. This method was developed to obtain conservative thresholds. During the test, the crack initiates from a cyclic compression precrack, which is open. The amplitude is increased in each step, eliminating the effect of overload due to PICC completely. The problem is that the methods developed for minimisation of PICC leads to maximisation of OICC in corroding steels. Thus, this technique produces the most non-conservative thresholds possible due to massive oxide debris development. Indeed, the cyclic R-curves reported by Maierhofer et al. [19] for the same material as Material_2 revealed an increasing threshold up to $8 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, which is more than what is usually obtained by load shedding. In addition, the increasing dependence of threshold on crack length stretches far beyond the expected short crack regime, in particular between 1 and 8 mm [17]. This means that practically the whole residual fatigue life would lie in a short crack regime, challenging the definition of a short crack. The interaction between OICC and RICC in the dependence of threshold on crack length is worth investigating, especially in semi-elliptical cracks, where the effect of OICC is expected to be increasing due to the effect of growing crack front width.

Three-dimensional aspects of fatigue cracks

Stress and strain fields around the crack tip as well as the plastic zones are important for studying of various mechanisms of fatigue crack propagation. These parameters are often measured by the full field techniques such as digital image correlation. The data are calibrated or compared to the results of numerical analyses. These computations or even analytical estimates are often done in 2D with the plane stress condition. It should be emphasised that the results from 2D plane stress analyses are incorrect with respect to the free surface of a 3D cracked body/specimen due to the corner point singularity. The real stress and strain field and all of the corresponding quantities such as the plastic zone shape and size or crack closure are different. Even the definition of the stress intensity factor is problematic here. In a 2D plane stress simulation the stress intensity factor is very well defined, which already shows the incompatibility of the two cases. A 3D computational analysis should be performed to obtain relevant data for the surface measurement techniques. This problem is associated with the real crack front shape, which depends on crack closure. Realistically curved crack fronts along the specimen thickness should be considered in order to obtain plastic zones, CTODs or crack closure, see, e.g. Oplt et al. [20].

CONCLUSIONS

A combined numerical-experimental approach was presented to bring more clarity into the issues associated with the scatter and non-conservativeness of residual fatigue life estimations, especially regarding the threshold testing procedures for corroding steels. The proposed measurement of the crack growth rate data in a dry air chamber is able to simulate operational conditions either at low loading frequency or low air humidity. In addition, it allows separation of the crack closure mechanisms and improvement of the simulations of the individual components. Implementation of them into a fatigue crack propagation model is a demanding process, for which several ideas were

proposed. The widely used NASGRO approach was kept functional, while the closure components were updated to reach more realistic predictions.

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